

Balancing Minds and Data: The Privacy Dilemma of LLMs and Anthropomorphism in LLMs

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Abstract: This essay examines the intricate relationship between large language models (LLMs) and privacy, investigating the ethical and practical issues stemming from cutting-edge artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. The research delves into the evolving understanding of privacy in the digital era, with a specific emphasis on the risks posed by anthropomorphic AI design. The analysis highlights critical privacy concerns: (1) Trust and accountability: The lack of true moral agency in AI systems complicates traditional notions of trust and responsibility; (2) Nissenbaum's Contextual Integrity Framework as a tool to explore privacy issues in general and with LLM; (3) Data collection challenges: LLMs collect extensive user data, often without explicit consent, potentially breaching contextual privacy norms; (4) Anthropomorphism risks: Human-like AI interfaces can foster over-trust, leading users to share sensitive information inappropriately. This article underscores that privacy is a complex, multidimensional concept profoundly shaped by technological, cultural, and social forces. As AI technologies continue to advance, safeguarding privacy will necessitate a nuanced approach that strikes a balance between individual rights, societal needs, and technological progress. We conclude with user-oriented guidelines and future research directions, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing the privacy implications of LLMs.

Key words: large language models (LLMs); privacy; anthropomorphic artificial intelligence (AI); trust calibration; contextual integrity; data protection; membership inference attack; human–AI interaction

I Introduction

The rise of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT and Claude has revolutionized natural language processing, transforming various industries from customer service to healthcare. However, this technological advancement introduces complex ethical and practical dilemmas, particularly concerning privacy and trust. This essay explores the intricate relationship between LLMs and privacy, utilizing modern

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theoretical frameworks, real-world examples, and future research directions.

The essay investigates the ethical and practical challenges posed by LLMs, with a focus on privacy, trust, and anthropomorphism. It begins by examining the concept of trust in artificial intelligence (AI) systems, highlighting the limitations of LLMs as non-accountable entities. The essay then delves into the multifaceted nature of privacy, incorporating historical and contemporary frameworks, before analyzing core privacy issues associated with LLM data practices. The risks of anthropomorphized AI, including over-trust and manipulation, are discussed in detail. The text concludes with guidelines for users and future research directions, offering a comprehensive framework for understanding and addressing the privacy implications of LLMs.

While much prior work has addressed either privacy or trust in AI systems, this essay offers a novel perspective by linking anthropomorphic design strategies to privacy vulnerabilities in LLMs. We extend Nissenbaum's Contextual Integrity Framework to show how seemingly benign trust cues—such as human-like voices or first-person language—can systematically mislead users and violate contextual privacy expectations. In doing so, we aim to bridge a critical gap between ethical design and data protection in generative AI.

2 Trust in AI Systems—The Nature of Trust

Trust is essential for the widespread adoption of AI technologies and has been extensively studied over the past 25 years^[1, 2]. At a fundamental level, trust involves a trustor who places confidence in a trustee regarding some object of trust^[3]. According to Ryan^[4], trust encompasses an affective attitude of confidence in the goodwill and competence of another, as well as an expectation that the trusted party will be directly and favorably moved by the thought that their trust is being counted on. However, LLMs challenge traditional notions of trust. For trust to be warranted, the trustee must be an appropriate subject of blame when that trust is breached^[4]. Placani^[5] contended that AI lacks moral agency and, therefore, cannot be truly trusted, as it cannot be held accountable for breaches or be held responsible for its actions.

Trust emerges as a fundamental human mechanism for navigating complex social interactions, serving as a cognitive shortcut that allows individuals to engage with uncertain environments by reducing perceived risk and complexity^[3, 4]. In the digital realm, this psychological construct takes on heightened significance, transforming from an interpersonal dynamic to a critical framework for understanding technological interactions and systemic relationships^[6, 7]. As digital technologies increasingly mediate our experiences, the concept of trust becomes a pivotal bridge connecting human intuition with technological engagement, setting the stage for a deeper exploration of privacy in an interconnected, data-driven world.

Recent research calls for a redefinition of trust in AI by introducing new typologies and frameworks widely

based on calibrated trust^[8–10], where users align their trust with the actual capabilities and trustworthiness of the system. Calibrated trust is dynamic and evidence-based, requiring users to adjust their level of trust in response to the observed reliability, transparency, and limitations of the AI—not in response to presumed motives or character traits, as in human relationships. This constitutes an important distinction that Lukyanenko et al.^[11] advanced in their foundational trust framework.

Choung et al.^[6] proposed a multidimensional definition of trust specific to AI and LLMs with two main components. The first is human-like trust, which relates to perceptions of benevolence, integrity, and ethical alignment—how much the AI seems to care, behave consistently, and align with social and moral norms. The second is functionality trust, which includes beliefs about the AI's competence, reliability, and technical performance. This dual perspective reflects the hybrid nature of AI systems: they function as both social actors (due to anthropomorphic traits) and technical tools.

Moreover, trust is not solely about technical performance but also about how human-like the system appears and how well it aligns with users' expectations of rational and ethical reasoning, as emphasized by Shin^[7]. Perceived humanness (e.g., natural language and emotional cues), transparency of algorithmic processes, and a sense of shared understanding all contribute to whether users feel comfortable delegating judgment or decision-making to the AI. Trust is shaped by both affective impressions and cognitive evaluations, making it a nuanced and dynamic psychological construct in human-AI interaction.

Related concepts include algorithmic trust, which reflects confidence in an AI system's functioning and explainability, and proxy trust, where users rely on external cues—like provider reputation, certifications, or regulatory compliance—due to limited technical understanding^[12–14].

These new trust typologies are designed to mitigate the risks of overtrust or undertrust and instead foster an appropriate, context-sensitive appraisal of AI's risks and affordances. Based on this, we propose a working definition of trust in LLMs as a user's calibrated reliance on the system's perceived reliability,

explainability, transparency, humanness, and cognitive alignment, as well as on indirect signals such as regulation or provider reputation.

To operationalize and evaluate such calibrated trust in practice, the trust calibration maturity model (TCMM) is a framework designed to assess and communicate the maturity of an AI system's trustworthiness across five key dimensions: performance characterization, bias and robustness quantification, transparency, safety and security, and usability^[15]. By systematically evaluating these areas, the TCMM provides stakeholders with a clear understanding of where a system stands in terms of trustworthy AI development. This model is used to guide both developers and users in calibrating their trust appropriately.

3 Understanding Privacy: Definition and Framework

Bridging the preceding discussion of trust in AI with the exploration of privacy, it becomes clear that the psychological mechanisms underpinning trust such as perceived reliability, transparency, and humanness directly shape how individuals approach the disclosure and protection of personal information in digital environments. As users increasingly rely on LLMs for sensitive tasks, understanding the evolving definitions and frameworks of privacy is essential for evaluating the unique risks and expectations that arise at the intersection of trust, data, and AI-driven technologies.

3.1 Historical foundation of privacy

The academic study of privacy can be traced back to Warren and Brandeis^[16], who famously conceptualized it as “the right to be left alone”. Their work established the foundation for modern privacy laws and highlighted the tension between individual privacy and societal needs. This early definition emphasized a physical and spatial understanding of privacy, reflecting the time when surveillance was primarily direct and visible. As technology advanced, the conceptualization of privacy evolved.

Westin's seminal work “Privacy and Freedom” shifted the focus towards information control, proposing that privacy entails an individual's ability to determine when, how, and to what extent their personal information is shared with others^[17]. Westin's definition remains widely cited, particularly in

discussions surrounding privacy in the digital age, where exercising control over personal data has become increasingly challenging.

3.2 Modern interpretation: Contextual Integrity Framework

In contemporary scholarship, Nissenbaum^[18] introduced the Contextual Integrity Framework, which conceptualizes privacy as the “appropriate flow of information”. In contrast to Westin's emphasis on individual control, Nissenbaum's framework focuses on the role of social norms and contextual factors in determining privacy violations. According to the Contextual Integrity Framework, privacy is maintained when information is shared within its intended context and adheres to the established principles of data transmission. For example, a patient disclosing medical history to a healthcare provider expects this information to remain within the healthcare domain. If this data is repurposed for marketing or shared with third parties, it would constitute a breach of privacy due to the violation of contextual norms.

The Contextual Integrity Framework is particularly relevant in the digital era, where data flows are complex and often opaque. Social media platforms, for instance, frequently push the boundaries of contextual integrity by repurposing user data for targeted advertising without explicit user consent.

3.3 Challenge of defining privacy, a multifaceted concept

The concept of privacy remains elusive, stemming from its inherently subjective and multidimensional nature. Holvast^[19] observed that privacy encompasses a wide range of dimensions, including solitude, anonymity, secrecy, and control over personal information, which can overlap but are not always aligned. As Holvast^[19] stated, “There is no common definition of privacy and the range is huge.”

Cultural differences significantly shape perceptions of privacy. In collectivist societies, privacy emphasizes maintaining group harmony, while individualistic cultures often prioritize personal autonomy and control over one's information^[20, 21]. While this distinction provides a useful starting point, it does not capture the full complexity of privacy concepts across cultures. For instance, in China, privacy is often subordinated to collective interests and state security,

as reflected in the widespread implementation of social credit systems^[22], whereas in Germany, historical experiences with surveillance have led to a strong emphasis on informational self-determination and data protection, reinforced by comprehensive regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Europe^[23]. In the United States, privacy is frequently framed as a safeguard against government intrusion, yet commercial data practices are comparatively less regulated. Additionally, many Indigenous communities view privacy not only as an individual right but also as a collective value, emphasizing the protection of communal knowledge and cultural heritage^[24].

Privacy, widely regarded as fundamental to individual autonomy and human dignity, has eluded precise definition despite significant scholarly efforts. Its complexity arises from its deeply contextual nature, shaped by cultural, social, legal, and technological factors. Privacy's relevance extends across diverse domains, including personal relationships, healthcare, finance, and digital communication, rendering it a dynamic and multifaceted construct. As Nissenbaum^[18] argued, privacy should be understood as “contextual integrity” reflecting the norms and expectations of specific social contexts.

3.4 Technological shift and privacy

The digital age has significantly complicated the notion of privacy. In the pre-digital era, privacy breaches were often tangible and visible, such as physical intrusions into personal space or unauthorized access to confidential documents. However, in the contemporary landscape, privacy violations frequently occur covertly through the collection, storage, and utilization of personal data by digital systems.

LLMs and other artificial intelligence technologies exemplify this paradigm shift. These systems rely on extensive datasets, frequently aggregated without explicit user consent, to train algorithms capable of natural language processing, image recognition, and various other functionalities. The scale and opacity of these data flows make it challenging for individuals to fully comprehend or exercise control over the use of their information, presenting new complexities for privacy protection.

For instance, when a user engages with an LLM like ChatGPT, they may share personal information during

the interaction. The user may assume that this exchange is private, akin to a one-on-one conversation. However, in reality, the data could be stored for model training or shared with third parties for performance optimization^[5]. Additionally, the data, particularly personal information, could be leveraged to construct user profiles and enhance targeted advertising. Furthermore, the potential for future applications involving these personal data collections further exacerbates the discrepancy between user expectations and actual data practices. This discrepancy underscores the growing relevance of frameworks such as the Contextual Integrity Framework in assessing privacy concerns in the digital domain.

3.5 Privacy in practice: Balancing trade-off

The multifaceted character of privacy necessitates balancing competing interests. For example, in the healthcare domain, sharing sensitive medical data can enhance diagnosis and personalized treatment, but it also heightens the risk of data breaches or misuse. Similarly, in the digital economy, consumers frequently trade privacy for convenience, such as utilizing free services that monetize user data through targeted advertising. These trade-offs emphasize the significance of transparency and informed consent. As Nissenbaum^[18] underscored, users must be cognizant of how their data are collected, utilized, and shared to make meaningful decisions about their privacy. However, achieving this transparency is challenging, as privacy policies are often lengthy, complex, and difficult for laypeople to comprehend, further complicating the user's ability to make informed choices.

3.6 Core privacy issue with LLMs, data collection, and usage

LLMs depend on extensive datasets, frequently encompassing user-generated content. Drapkin^[25] underscored how ChatGPT's privacy policy allows for the sharing of personal data with the third parties without explicit user consent, raising concerns about transparency and accountability. Such practices can violate contextual privacy norms, as exemplified in medical use cases where users anticipate confidentiality akin to a patient-physician relationship. Applying Nissenbaum's Contextual Integrity Framework, key elements such as the involved actors,

the types of information, and the transmission principles are often contravened in LLM interactions. For example:

- **Actors:** Users expect only the AI to process their data, yet developers or external systems often have access.

- **Information types:** Sensitive information, such as health data, is sometimes repurposed for model training, violating privacy expectations.

- **Transmission principles:** Implicit assumptions about confidentiality are undermined when data are shared with third parties under less stringent terms.

These theoretical concerns have been echoed in real-world legal developments. In late 2023, *The New York Times* filed a landmark lawsuit against OpenAI and Microsoft, alleging that ChatGPT reproduced substantial portions of its copyrighted content without permission. Although the lawsuit centers on copyright, it has far-reaching implications for data governance, transparency, and privacy in generative AI since “OpenAI is now directed to preserve and segregate all output log data that would otherwise be deleted on a going forward basis until further order of the Court (in essence, the output log data that OpenAI has been destroying), whether such data might be deleted at a user’s request or because of (numerous privacy laws and regulations) that might require OpenAI to do so”^[26]. As a result, OpenAI is currently required to indefinitely store all user-provided data—including personal and sensitive information—regardless of its own privacy policy or overarching data protection regulations such as GDPR in Europe.

In addition to legal and regulatory challenges, LLMs also face technical vulnerabilities that directly compromise user privacy. A particularly concerning technical risk to privacy in LLMs arises from Membership Inference Attacks (MIAs)^[27, 28]. In such attacks, adversaries attempt to determine whether a specific data point—such as a user’s input or personal record—was part of a model’s training dataset. By analyzing the model’s output behavior (e.g., prediction confidence or response variance), attackers can exploit statistical patterns that differ between data the model has seen and data it has not.

Membership inference attacks based on self-calibrated probabilistic variation (SPV-MIA) against fine-tuned LLMs can now reach an area under curve (AUC)

of up to 0.9, representing a very high level of attack success^[29, 30]. These findings demonstrate that even large, broadly trained AI models are not immune to membership inference attacks, posing a serious privacy concern and highlighting the urgent need for effective mitigation strategies.

Recent research has revealed a multitude of additional acute privacy risks associated with LLMs^[31], and developed a taxonomy of security threats that emphasizes the importance of further developing robust, multi-layered security strategies to ensure the safety and usefulness of LLMs. In data poisoning, for example, attackers inject malicious or biased data into the training corpus. Attackers can manipulate model outputs or implant backdoors, undermining both privacy and reliability. Additionally, reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) processes, while intended to align model behavior with human values, can inadvertently leak private information if user feedback or conversational data is not properly anonymized or filtered, as documented in recent surveys of LLM security and privacy incidents.

All these vulnerabilities pose a substantial privacy threat, especially when LLMs are trained on sensitive or proprietary information, as it may allow for the unintended exposure of individuals’ participation in a dataset without their consent. Given the opaque nature of LLM training processes and the growing use of such models in domains like healthcare, education, and law, the cases highlight the urgent need for robust privacy-preserving techniques, stricter audit mechanisms in model development and deployment and secure, audit-ready AI deployments.

3.7 Summary: Privacy

Privacy is a multifaceted and dynamic concept, shaped by technological, cultural, and societal forces. While earlier conceptions emphasized individual control, contemporary approaches like Nissenbaum’s Contextual Integrity Framework stress the significance of context in defining privacy violations. As technologies such as LLMs continue to evolve, safeguarding privacy will necessitate a nuanced approach that judiciously balances individual rights, societal needs, and the potential benefits of innovation.

The subjective nature of privacy emerges as a critical consideration in discussions surrounding AI and LLMs.

Privacy, far from being a monolithic concept, is inherently subjective and multifaceted, shaped by individual perceptions and cultural contexts. What one person deems private may be considered public by another, underscoring the complexity of establishing universal privacy standards.

Cultural differences play a significant role in shaping privacy perceptions, extending beyond the individualistic–collectivist dichotomy. As previously discussed, countries like Germany emphasize informational self-determination due to historical surveillance experiences, whereas China, for instance, tends to subordinate privacy to collective interests and state control. This cultural variability adds another layer of complexity to privacy considerations in the global context of AI development and deployment.

Therefore, privacy encompasses various aspects such as solitude, anonymity, secrecy, and control over personal information. These dimensions, while often overlapping, are not always perfectly aligned, further complicating efforts to define and protect privacy uniformly. Nissenbaum’s Contextual Integrity Framework provides a valuable lens for understanding privacy, emphasizing that privacy is maintained when information flows adhere to established norms within their intended contexts.

Further, the concept of privacy has evolved significantly over time, transitioning from a primarily physical and spatial understanding to a more complex notion centered on information control^[17] or appropriate flow of information^[18] in the digital age. This evolution reflects the changing landscape of technology and its impact on personal data.

In practice, privacy often involves a delicate balancing act between competing interests. Individuals frequently find themselves trading personal data for convenience or improved services, particularly in the digital economy. This trade-off signals the need for a nuanced approach to privacy protection that considers both individual rights and the potential benefits of data-driven technologies.

4 Anthropomorphism and Privacy Risk

The intricate relationship between trust and privacy, as explored in previous sections, illuminates the critical challenges posed by anthropomorphic AI design.

As the focus shifts to examining the risks of

anthropomorphism, it is important to recognize how human-like AI attributes can exploit inherent trust mechanisms, potentially compromising privacy in ways that transcend traditional data collection concerns.

4.1 Privacy risk by cultivating user trust

Anthropomorphic design, which assigns human-like characteristics to AI systems, often enhances user trust and has become a prominent strategy in artificial intelligence. Deshpande et al.^[32] suggested that such an approach can improve usability and accessibility, particularly in domains such as customer service, healthcare, and education. Building on this, recent studies have demonstrated that anthropomorphic elements can also increase user engagement, perceived social presence, and task performance—especially in sensitive applications like mental health and therapeutic support^[33].

Moreover, for diverse global audiences, emotionally intelligent chatbot design—driven by anthropomorphic visual features and the perception of intelligence mediated through empathy and trust—has been shown to significantly improve user experience^[34]. Such design choices foster more relatable and inclusive interactions, making LLM-based systems accessible far beyond a technical or intellectual elite.

However, this increased trust can lead to over-reliance, with users sharing sensitive information under a mistaken belief in the system’s security. For instance, a chatbot that simulates empathy may inadvertently encourage users, especially those who are vulnerable, to disclose sensitive data inappropriately.

This dynamic becomes even more pronounced in the context of LLMs, which people now regularly interact with via multimodal interfaces, including both speech and text (e.g., Bard). In a large-scale online experiment involving 2165 participants aged 18 to 90 from the United States, researchers tested how modality (text-only vs. speech + text) and grammatical person (“I” vs. “the system”) influenced user perceptions. Results showed that the inclusion of speech significantly increased anthropomorphism and led to higher perceived accuracy of the information provided by the LLM^[35]. These findings underscore the persuasive power of anthropomorphic cues and highlight the need for careful design choices, especially in high-stakes domains such as healthcare. For instance,

generated voices should be reserved for contexts where the system's confidence in the accuracy of its information is high; otherwise, incorporating cues of uncertainty and explicit source attribution is recommended. Moreover, while the use of first-person pronouns did not have as strong an effect as speech overall, it still contributed to increased trust in specific contexts, such as medication-related information, and should therefore be considered with caution.

These findings shed light on a broader concern: users who engage with AI systems that emulate human behavior may attribute undue intelligence, empathy, or trustworthiness to them. Placani^[5] emphasized that this dynamic is particularly problematic in vulnerable populations, such as children, the elderly, or people who are under pressure to perform. For instance, an elderly user might develop a parasocial relationship with a chatbot designed to provide companionship, leading to the over-sharing of sensitive health or financial information. Similarly, children interacting with anthropomorphic AI in educational settings may disclose personal or family details without fully comprehending the implications for their privacy and data security.

The risks of anthropomorphic over-trust are further illustrated by a case documented by Guinzburg^[36], in which a ChatGPT repeatedly apologized for not reading her work, promised to do so, and yet continued to fail at the task. Despite not accessing or evaluating the text, the system generated trust through anthropomorphic design features—such as expressions of gratitude, praise, and validation (humanization)—as well as cognitively coherent and seemingly insightful feedback. These cues fostered a sense of reliability and care, even though the underlying system never actually engaged with the content. This illustrates how trust can be promoted “by design” as a general principle, rather than being acquired through argumentation or evidence-based interaction arising from the situation and raises critical concerns about the ethical implications of embedding trust-inducing features into AI systems that lack genuine comprehension or accountability.

A final example of misplaced trust driven by anthropomorphic cues occurred when the *Chicago Sun-Times* published a summer reading list generated by AI,

which included ten entirely fabricated book titles attributed to real authors^[37]. Here again, human-like cues, a confident tone, and linguistic coherence masked fundamental deficiencies in reasoning and fact-checking. The episode demonstrates how anthropomorphic design in LLMs not only influences individual user trust, but can also mislead entire institutions, posing serious risks in public communication, journalism, and beyond.

4.2 Manipulative capability

Anthropomorphic design can also be leveraged in manipulative ways. AI systems tailored to emulate empathy or understanding may subtly influence user behavior, leading to outcomes as follows:

- **Increased data sharing:** By appearing more relatable, anthropomorphic AI may normalize invasive data practices, conditioning users to share more personal information over time.
- **Targeted advertising:** A chatbot simulating human-like rapport might guide users toward specific products or services, leveraging trust to influence purchasing decisions.
- **Behavioral conditioning:** Prolonged interactions with anthropomorphic systems can condition users to rely on these systems for decision-making, reducing critical engagement and increasing dependence.

As Deshpande et al.^[32] caution, the use of manipulative practices in anthropomorphic AI design can obscure ethical boundaries, especially when users lack awareness of the system's underlying objectives. Companies such as OpenAI and Anthropic have leveraged anthropomorphic design as a strategy to enhance the trustworthiness and acceptability of their AI systems^[6, 7, 38, 39].

4.3 Illusion of security

Another significant risk is the illusion of security created by anthropomorphic AI. Users may mistakenly believe that an AI system will respect privacy norms akin to a human professional, such as a doctor or lawyer. However, if the system stores, shares, or uses data for purposes like model training or third-party analytics, it fundamentally violates these expectations. This mismatch between user assumptions and actual practices erodes trust and amplifies privacy risks. Furthermore, LLMs often do not provide complete

information about their trustworthiness or the personal data they process. For instance, Snapchat fails to disclose that a user's location is processed when inquiring about the data collected by their chatbot, only revealing this information when explicitly asked^[38].

4.4 Societal implication

The widespread adoption of anthropomorphic AI may also influence societal attitudes towards privacy over time. As proposed by Placani^[5], users' familiarity with human-like AI systems may lead them to become more comfortable with sharing personal data, potentially eroding existing privacy standards. Furthermore, the attribution of moral agency to these anthropomorphic systems risks undermining accountability and sustaining misconceptions about AI's true capabilities.

4.5 Summary: Anthropomorphism and privacy risks

Anthropomorphic AI design, while potentially enhancing user experience and engagement, also introduces significant privacy risks that necessitate careful management. Challenges such as over-trust, manipulative capabilities, and the erosion of privacy norms require transparent system design, robust ethical guidelines, and comprehensive user education. Only through the implementation of these mitigating measures can the potential benefits of anthropomorphic AI be responsibly harnessed.

5 Guidelines for Users

As a result of our previous findings, users should proactively adopt strategies to mitigate privacy risks associated with anthropomorphic AI systems.

- **Understand AI limitations:** Recognize that anthropomorphic systems are not sentient and cannot guarantee privacy. Trust in LLMs should not be blind or anthropomorphic. Instead, it should be based on evidence such as published privacy policies, technical audits, and regulatory compliance.
- **Critically assess data sharing:** Avoid oversharing sensitive information, particularly in high-stakes contexts like healthcare or finance.
- **Regularly review privacy settings:** Ensure that data-sharing permissions align with personal preferences and expectations.

- **Apply Nissenbaum's Contextual Integrity Framework:** Evaluate whether data flows adhere to contextual norms before engaging with AI tools.

- **Assess and calibrate trust according to the TCMM.**

These guidelines provide users with strategies to mitigate privacy risks while harnessing the advantages of large language models. As a further step toward developing targeted guidance for particular vulnerable user populations, we have provisionally compiled [Table I](#) "recommended privacy practices by user group" to illustrate context-sensitive best practices.

6 Future Research Directions

As anthropomorphic artificial intelligence becomes increasingly integrated into daily life, future research must address key challenges to ensure its ethical and responsible utilization. Developing comprehensive ethical guidelines for anthropomorphized AI is critical to prevent potential exploitation, particularly among vulnerable populations. Research efforts should explore the impact of anthropomorphism on user trust and behavior, examining how human-like traits influence data sharing practices, reliance, and emotional attachment.

Privacy remains a central concern, necessitating the development of improved privacy protection mechanisms for AI systems. Innovative solutions such as encryption and anonymization techniques could mitigate privacy risks while preserving AI's core functionality. Additionally, research into the privacy implications of conversational AI in sensitive contexts, including healthcare and finance, can inform strategies to safeguard users.

The establishment of robust legal frameworks for human-like AI is equally important, clarifying accountability and compliance with privacy laws. This includes investigating potential biases and discrimination within anthropomorphized AI systems, ensuring equitable treatment across demographic groups. It could also be interesting to examine whether it would be possible and useful at the regulatory and political level to explicitly de-anthropomorphize (which may be required at the legal level).

Understanding user behavior in response to AI-generated personalized content will help address

Table 1 User-group-specific privacy risks in LLM use and targeted mitigation practices. Citations indicate supporting literature already included in the references list.

User group	Main privacy risk	Concrete action / best practice
General user	Accidental disclosure of sensitive data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid sharing sensitive personal data (e.g., health, financial, and passwords); use pseudonyms where personal identifiers are unavoidable^[25]. • Review and understand the platform’s privacy policy and data usage terms^[5]. • Use privacy-focused platforms (e.g., local LLMs, and browser-based tools)^[31]. • Log out and clear chat history after use; regularly check and adjust AI permissions and retention settings.
Children and teens	Low awareness of privacy risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use AI systems only with adult supervision^[5]. • Avoid entering real names, addresses, or school information^[25]. • Prefer child-friendly, privacy-conscious tools. • Discuss privacy concerns with a parent or teacher before sharing information. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build digital literacy and understand basic data privacy.
Elderly	Misplaced trust due to anthropomorphism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seek help understanding privacy terms and AI behavior^[5]. • Never share ID numbers, banking info, or login data. • Use only trusted platforms, ideally recommended by caregivers and enable device-level privacy protections^[35]. • Check in regularly with family or trusted individuals about AI usage.
Professionals (e.g., healthcare, legal, and education)	Breach of confidentiality obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Never input client, case, or confidential data into public AI tools^[31]. • Use enterprise-grade or self-hosted systems with compliance guarantees (GDPR/HIPAA-compliant, access-controlled, and audit logging). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document AI-supported decision processes^[31]. • Consult data protection officers when unsure.
Developers and model providers	Model inversion or membership leaks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement privacy-by-design principles, including data minimization and differential privacy^[31]. • Provide clear, context-sensitive privacy notices and reminders during interactions. • Run recurring security-and-privacy audits to detect leakage, membership inference, data poisoning, or prompt-injection—and patch immediately^[27, 29, 30]. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow users to access, correct, or delete their data easily. • Use synthetic or anonymized data for model training whenever possible^[27].
Policymakers and Regulators	Opaque data flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandate transparency in AI data practices and anthropomorphic features^[18]. • Require regular third-party audits of LLM systems for privacy and security compliance^[14]. • Develop guidelines for responsible reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) processes, including privacy-preserving feedback mechanisms^[31]. • Encourage public reporting mechanisms for privacy breaches and misuse.

privacy risks tied to data-driven interactions. Lastly, long-term studies on the psychological effects of human-like AI, including emotional attachment and dependency, are essential to assess its broader societal impact and guide responsible development. These research efforts will shape the ethical, legal, and technological future of anthropomorphic AI.

7 Conclusion

The intersection of LLMs and privacy presents both opportunities and challenges. While these systems offer transformative capabilities, their reliance on vast amounts of user data raises critical ethical questions. By applying frameworks like Nissenbaum’s Contextual Integrity Framework, fostering user awareness, and

advancing ethical and technical safeguards, society can navigate the privacy dilemma without compromising innovation.

Beyond these general insights, this essay offers two specific contributions. First, we propose a working definition of trust in LLMs as a user’s calibrated reliance on reliability, explainability, transparency, humanness, cognitive alignment, and indirect signals, such as regulation or provider reputation. This conceptualization provides researchers and practitioners with a structured framework for evaluating when trust is warranted and when it may be misplaced. Second, we introduce user-oriented privacy guidelines tailored to different target groups, including children, the elderly, professionals, and policymakers,

thereby illustrating the value of context-sensitive approaches.

Together, these contributions extend current debates by translating theoretical frameworks into actionable guidance for research and practice. Looking ahead, advancing this agenda will require interdisciplinary efforts integrating technical innovation, ethical design, and regulatory foresight to ensure the future of LLMs strengthens, rather than undermines, privacy.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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